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**INFLUENCE OF ECDISTEN ON LIPID
METABOLISM IN EXPERIMENTAL ALLOXAN
DIABETES**

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Relevance. According to the World Health Organization, there are 150 million people in the world suffering from diabetes [1]. The great social significance of this disease lies in the fact that its late complications (micro- and macroangiopathies) lead to disability of patients and deaths. In diabetes, the risk of cardiovascular disorders increases by 2-4 times, which in people with type 2 diabetes (DM 2) cause 75% of the total morbidity and mortality. Diabetes accelerates the development of atherosclerosis, which often begins even before the onset of clinical signs and the establishment of hyperglycemia. At the time of detection of diabetes, half of the patients already have coronary heart disease. This demonstrates the importance of early diagnosis and intensive treatment of hyperglycemia and related disorders. The formation of plaques and atherosclerotic changes in the coronary arteries, cerebral and peripheral vessels also increase. Patients with diabetes, especially women, have increased mortality due to cardiovascular disorders. In diabetes, the effectiveness of procedures such as angioplasty and coronary revascularization is reduced.

A 7-year study of a large population in Finland showed that myocardial infarction (MI) in diabetic patients who had not previously had MI was as common as in people without diabetes who had had MI [2]. Because of the close relationship between diabetes and cardiovascular disease (CVD) at the

epidemiological and pathophysiological levels, the National Adult Cholesterol Extension Program (NCEP AN P-III) defines diabetes as a risk equivalent.

The American Diabetes Association (ADA) recommends a lipid spectrum study that includes total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides, low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol, and high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol at the time of diagnosis of type 2 diabetes. In the absence of lipid metabolism disorders, a second study is carried out annually. In patients who remain at low risk of developing CVD, a lipid spectrum study can be performed once every 2 years

Purpose of research. Goal of the work. Study of lipid metabolism disorders and evaluation of the effect of ecdisten on lipid metabolism in experimental alloxan diabetes (AD).

Materials and research methods. The experiments were carried out on 70 male rats weighing 130-150 g, kept on a standard diet. When performing experiments, we were guided by the "European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals Used for Experiments and Other Scientific Purposes" (Strasbourg, 1985). To reproduce the model of diabetes, 60 rats after quarantine were injected with alloxan at a dose of 13 mg per 100 g of weight once. The development of diabetes was judged by the content of glucose in the blood, which was determined on a biochemical analyzer using a set of glucose oxidase tests from Lahema. 7 days after the reproduction of diabetes, the animals were divided into 4 groups of 15 each: 1st (control) - rats with AD, who received distilled water orally at a dose of 0.5 ml per 100 g of body weight; group 2 (main) - rats with AD treated with ecdisten at a dose of 0.143 mg per 100 g of body weight intragastrically; group 3 - rats with AD treated with the reference drug Glucophage at a dose of 4.28 mg per 100 g of body weight; group 4 - rats with AD treated with the reference drug retabolil at a dose of 0.0714 mg per 100 g of body weight. The preparations were administered within 14 days, the animals were slaughtered on the 14th and 21st days from the beginning of the experiment. The intact group consisted of 10 rats. The choice of reference drugs is justified

by the fact that glucophage is practically the only antidiabetic drug that reduces the risk of death from diabetes and its serious complications. It reduces the rate of absorption of carbohydrates in the small intestine, increases the sensitivity of peripheral tissues to insulin, inhibits the processes of gluconeogenesis and glycogenolysis in the liver, and reduces systemic hyperinsulinemia. Retabolil, like ecdisten, has an anabolic effect.

Lipid metabolism parameters were determined using human biolatests (Germany) in the clinical department of MITL TMA (head of the laboratory - Ph.D. E.Kh. Azizov).

When processing the obtained results, the applied programs Statistica 6, Biostat were used. Data are presented as arithmetic means (M) and standard deviations (m). The samples were compared using the Student's t-test or the paired Wilcoxon test. The significance level was considered significant at $P < 0.05$.

Results and discussion. The main characteristics of dyslipidemia in type 2 diabetes are an increase in the level of triglycerides in the composition of very low density lipoproteins (VLDL) and a decrease in the level of HDL cholesterol. The concentration of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol in patients with DM practically does not differ from that in persons without this disease, however, in patients with type 2 DM, the fraction of small dense LDL, which have increased atherogenicity due to their high ability to oxidize, predominates. Quantitative changes in the lipid spectrum can occur in isolation, but more often they are combined and are called the lipid triad, or atherogenic dyslipidemia.

The indicators of lipid metabolism are shown in table 1. As can be seen from table 1, the content of total cholesterol with the introduction of alloxan for 7 days does not change significantly. On the 14th and 21st days of alloxan administration, the content of total cholesterol was 22.5 and 55% higher, respectively, than in animals of the intact group. With the introduction of ecdisten for 7 and 14 days, the content of total cholesterol was lower than in animals that

were not injected with ecdisten, respectively, by 22.5 and 28.5%, i.e. the most pronounced decrease in total cholesterol occurs during treatment with ecdysten for 14 days.

Treatment with glucophage for 7 and 14 days led to a decrease in total cholesterol compared to animals that were not injected with glucophage, by 13.4 and 32.8%, respectively. When treated with retabolil for 7 days, the content of total cholesterol increased by 37.9% compared with the untreated group, and in subsequent periods (up to 14 days) no significant changes in its content were recorded.

Thus, in animals with alloxan diabetes, ecdisten leads to a more pronounced decrease in total cholesterol than glucophage, and retabolil does not have a corrective effect.

As for triglycerides, on the 14th and 21st days of the development of experimental alloxan diabetes, its level was 1.6 and 3.0 times higher than in intact animals. Treatment with ecdysten for 7 days does not cause significant changes in the content of triglycerides compared with untreated animals. After 14 days from the start of treatment, the content of triglycerides compared with the untreated group is reduced by 2.1 times. Comparator drug glucophage during treatment for 7 and 14 days compared with the untreated group reduces the content of triglycerides, respectively, by 1.4 and 2.1 times. When treated with retabolil for only 14 days, the content of triglycerides is reduced by 1.4 times compared with the untreated group.

The main cause of hypertriglyceridemia in type 2 diabetes is the low sensitivity of visceral adipose tissue to the anti-lipolytic action of insulin, which leads to increased lipolysis, the entry of large amounts of free fatty acids into the portal circulation, and, in combination with hyperinsulinemia, an increase in the synthesis of triglycerides and VLDL by the liver. In addition, in patients with type 2 diabetes with hyperglycemia, the activity of endothelial lipoprotein lipase,

which is responsible for the catabolism of triglycerides and VLDL, is reduced, which exacerbates this disorder [4].

Thus, with the development of alloxan diabetes, the most pronounced increase in the level of triglycerides occurs on the 21st day of its development. In the treatment of ecdysten for 14 days, there is a more pronounced decrease in the level of triglycerides than with the introduction of glucophage and retabolil.

A study of the content of lipoprotein cholesterol showed that a more pronounced increase in the level of VLDL-C was observed on the 14th and 21st days of the development of alloxan diabetes by 1.7 and 2.6 times, respectively, compared with intact animals. Treatment with ecdysten and glucophage for 14 days more pronouncedly reduces the content of VLDL cholesterol (1.7 times) compared with the intact group. Retabolil does not cause significant changes in the content of VLDL-C during treatment for 7 and 14 days.

The content of LDL-C on the 7th, 14th and 21st days of the development of alloxan diabetes exceeds the values of the animals of the intact group by 42.8, 71.1 and 84.5%, respectively. In the treatment of ecdysten and glucophage for 7 and 14 days, the content of LDL cholesterol decreases by 2.0 and 1.8, respectively; 2.4 and 2.9 times. At the same time, no significant changes in this indicator were observed during treatment with retabolil.

When studying lipoproteins, much attention was paid to HDL. When determining the content of HDL-C in experimental animals, an unreliable decrease in it was revealed on the 7th day of the development of alloxan diabetes. On the 14th and 21st days of the experiment, this indicator was lower than in intact animals by 16.7 and 32.5%, respectively. In the treatment of ecdysten for 7 and 14 days, the content of HDL cholesterol compared with untreated animals increased by 2.7 and 3.9 times, respectively. At the same time, under the influence of glucophage and retabolil, the content of HDL cholesterol in all periods of the study increased slightly compared to the untreated group. These

data indicate that ecdysten contributes to a more pronounced increase in HDL-C than glucophage and ecdysten.

On the basis of the data obtained, we calculated the cholesterol coefficient of atherogenicity, which, as our observations showed, was lower than in intact animals at all stages of the development of experimental alloxan diabetes, respectively, by 2.1; 1.9 and 1.4 times. Compared with the group of untreated animals, ecdysten reduces the atherogenic coefficient on the 7th and 14th days of treatment by 3.1 and 4.4 times. A less pronounced decrease in this coefficient is observed in the treatment with glucophage; within 7 and 14 days, the atherogenic coefficient decreased only by 1.4 and 1.37 times. At the same time, treatment with retabolil led to an increase in this coefficient compared to the untreated group by 4.5 and 4.1 times, respectively.

According to the literature, the dyslipidemic profile of patients with type 2 diabetes is characterized by an elevated level of triglycerides and LDL and an increased concentration of HDL cholesterol. Numerous studies support the need for aggressive therapy with hyperlipidemia-lowering agents in all patients, and especially in those with diabetes. Dosages of drugs should provide the maximum effect, and in the absence of the desired result of monotherapy, combination treatment should be resorted to. According to the results of recent studies, in order to reduce the incidence of cardiovascular diseases and mortality from them among these patients, it is necessary to achieve a decrease in the concentration of LDL to 70 mg% and below.

According to the ADA recommendations, the main goal of treating dyslipidemia in type 2 diabetes is to reduce LDL-C to <100 mg/dl (2.6 mmol/l) [5]. LDL-C was chosen as the main parameter of the lipid spectrum due to the fact that, according to large-scale prospective studies, it is the decrease in LDL-C that is associated with a significant decrease in the occurrence of cardiovascular events and mortality from them. The ADA recommends the appointment of patients with type 2 diabetes only non-drug therapy with an LDL-C level of 100-

129 mg / dl and the absence of CVD (Table 1) for a period of 3-6 months with a repeated study of the lipid spectrum every 6 weeks and a final decision on the issue of prescribing drug therapy. At the level of LDL-C ≥ 130 mg / dl in patients with type 2 diabetes without CVD, medication is prescribed simultaneously with non-drug therapy. The same tactic is recommended by ADA for LDL-C >100 mg/dL in patients with type 2 diabetes and CVD [5].

Table 1.

Indicators of lipid metabolism in rats with alloxan diabetes

Indicators	Intact group	AD+H ₂ O, n=7			AD+Ec disten n=7		AD+glucophage, n=7		AD+retbolil, n=7	
		7 days	14 days	21 days	14 days	21 days	14 days	21 days	14 days	21 days
Total cholesterol mmol/l	4,0±0,27	3,93±0,07	4,75±0,08*	6,2±0,2*	3,8±0,2	4,4±0,18	4,23±0,17	4,2±0,74	6,8±0,54*	6,38±0,4*
Triglycerides mmol/l	1,22±0,13	0,83±0,14	2,06±0,08*	3,72±0,76*	1,65±0,19	1,77±0,08*	1,51±0,06*	1,75±0,07*	2,52±0,28*	2,65±0,16*
HDL cholesterol 0.7-1.73 mmol/l	1,2±0,08	1,1±0,13	1,0±0,1	0,81±0,07*	2,72±0,15*	3,2±0,32*	1,85±0,04*	1,87±0,02*	1,05±0,08	0,81±0,11*
LDL-C mmol/l	2,43±0,11	3,78±0,14*	4,2±0,2*	4,52±0,33*	2,05±0,05*	2,47±0,08	1,72±0,07*	1,58±0,02*	4,59±0,04*	4,32±0,06*

VLDL-C mmol/l	0,55± 0,02	0,67 ±0, 24	0,92 ±0,0 4*	1,42 ±0,2 *	0,72 ±0,0 8*	0,8± 0,04 *	0,69 ±0,0 2*	0,8± 0,04 *	1,12 ±0,1 4*	1,17 ±0,0 9*
Cholesterol coefficient. Atherogenic cholesterol/H DL	2,35± 0,22	2,57 ±0, 22	3,75 ±0,1 2*	6,65 ±0,1 *	0,40 ±0,0 5*	0,37 ±0,0 1*	1,28 ±0,0 6	1,25 ±0,2 3*	5,5± 0,67 *	6,9± 0,64 *

Note. * - P<0.5 compared with the intact group.

Thus, the treatment of experimental animals with alloxan diabetes with ecdysten and glucophage for 14 and 21 days more significantly reduces the content of triglycerides compared to the control. If on the 7th day of treatment the level of triglycerides had only a tendency to exceed the values of intact rats, then by the 14th day this indicator did not differ significantly from the normative values. Treatment with retabolil slightly reduces the concentration of triglycerides compared with the control. The concentration of HDL-C on the 14-21st day of treatment with retabolil was sharply reduced compared to the indices of animals in the control and intact groups, but treatment with ecdisten and glucophage, especially ecdisten, increased the concentration of HDL-C almost 2 times compared with the control. As for triglycerides, treatment with ecdysten and glucophage of experimental animals with alloxan diabetes for 14 and 21 days significantly reduces their content, while retabolil increases it.

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